

Multiscale AM-FM Image Reconstructions Based on Elastic Net Regression and Gabor Filterbanks

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Abstract—The paper proposes the use of elastic net regression for reconstructing images from AM-FM components. Current AM-FM reconstruction methods are based on Dominant Component Analysis (DCA), multi-scale DCA, and Channel Component Analysis (CCA). The paper introduces a variation on CCA that uses elastic net regression to minimize the number of channels that are used in the reconstruction. The new approach is validated using a family of Gabor filterbanks that is parameterized by an overlap index. The results show that the elastic net regression component selection algorithm performs significantly better than multiscale DCA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been renewed interest in the use of multi-scale AM-FM representations following the introduction of new AM-FM demodulation methods summarized in [1]. A summary of several applications of the new multi-scale AM-FM methods can be found in the recently published survey paper [2].

Earlier work with AM-FM models had demonstrated its promise with textured images, as in the example of fingerprint image classification [3], tree image analysis analyzing growth seasons [4], non-stationary wood-grain characterization [5], and other texture images [6]. The introduction of a multiscale approach in [1] demonstrated that the method can be used to reconstruct general images. In particular, a multi-scale AM-FM representation led to the important application of population screening for diabetic retinopathy as documented in [7], hysteroscopy image assessment [8], fMRI and MRI image analysis [9], and atherosclerotic plaque ultrasound image and video analysis [10]. Alternatively, the definition of multi-dimensional AM-FM transforms over curvilinear coordinate systems has led to the earlier development of very low bitrate video coding as demonstrated in [11],[12].

Formally, an input image $I(x, y)$ is expressed as a sum of AM-FM components as given by:

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^{n=M} a_n(x, y) \cos(\varphi_n(x, y)) \quad (1)$$

where n is used to index different AM-FM components, $a_n(x, y)$ denote the Instantaneous Amplitude (IA) functions, and $\varphi_n(x, y)$ denote the instantaneous phase (IP) functions.

There are different AM-FM demodulation methods that are focused on extracting IA and IP functions from any given image. Extracting IA and IP functions involves the 2D analytic extension of the image followed by the application of a multiscale filterbank [13]. Over each filterbank channel, the IA and the IP functions are estimated from the outputs. The goal of this paper is to explore sparse reconstructions based on the extracted IA and IP functions.

There are currently three methods for reconstructing AM-FM images from their components. First, in Channel Component Analysis (CCA) [13], the outputs from all of the filters are used in the reconstruction. Second, in Dominant Component Analysis (DCA) [13], a single AM-FM image is reconstructed pixel-by-pixel by selecting the IA and the IP from the channel that gives the largest IA value at each pixel. Third, in multiscale Dominant Component Analysis (mDCA) [1], the filterbank channels are grouped into scales, the DCA is applied to each scale, and the image is reconstructed from the components extracted from each scale. The current paper explores the use of a sparse representation for CCA over a family of Gabor filterbanks. The Gabor filterbank family is parameterized based on the overlap index. Assuming the same number of components, the proposed method is shown to outperform multiscale DCA. The approach is based on AM-FM component selection using elastic net regression [14]. The significant advantages of the proposed approach are demonstrated image reconstruction examples.

The rest of the paper is broken into three sections. Section II summarizes the relevant AM-FM methodology and the use of elastic net regression. The results and discussion are given in Section III. Concluding remarks are given in Section IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. AM-FM Decompositions

As described in the introduction, an AM-FM representation considers an image approximation based on

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^{n=M} a_n(x, y) \cos(\varphi_n(x, y)) \quad (2)$$

where $a_n(x, y) \cos \varphi_n(x, y)$ represent the AM-FM components. To estimate the IA and the IP, we begin with

$$I_{AS}(x, y) = I(x, y) + jH_{2d}[I(x, y)] \quad (3)$$

where denotes the 2D extension of 1D Hilbert transform operator. The resulting signal is processed through a filterbank. Then for each bandpass filter output we perform the estimation of IA and IP using:

$$a_n(x, y) = |I_{ASn}(x, y)|, \quad \text{and} \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_n(x, y) = \arctan \left(\frac{\text{imag}(I_{ASn}(x, y))}{\text{real}(I_{ASn}(x, y))} \right). \quad (5)$$

B. A family of Gabor filterbanks based on the overlap index

A family of Gabor filterbanks will be used for demonstrating AM-FM reconstructions. First, the number of orientations is fixed to eight. Second, for each orientation, along the radial line that goes through the center of each filter, the spread of each filter is varied so as to control the overlap. In the standard Gabor filterbank terminology, these filters are often intersected at half-peak. The half-peak choice corresponds to an overlap index of 0.5 in our terminology. Here, we fix the radial magnitude of the central frequency as given in Table I. In constant-Q filtering, the ratio of the central frequency divided by the bandwidth of each filter is held constant. By varying Q, we can achieve different overlaps. Here, we define the overlap index to denote the mean overlap, and vary the overlap index from 0.365 to 0.867 to avoid both low and excessive overlap.

TABLE I

GABOR FILTERBANK FAMILY CHARACTERISTICS. ALL FILTERBANKS MAINTAINED SIX SCALES FROM VERY VERY LOW FREQUENCIES TO VERY HIGH FREQUENCIES AND EIGHT CONSTANT ORIENTATIONS. OVERALL, THE FILTERBANK CONSISTS OF 41 FILTERS.

Scales	Radial Center of Gabor Filter (Freq)	Num. of Orientations
Very-Very Low (VVL)	0	1
Very Low (VL)	$\pi/16$	8
Low (L)	$\pi/8$	8
Medium (M)	$\pi/4$	8
High (H)	$\pi/2$	8
Very High (VH)	$3\pi/4$	8

C. Elastic Net Regression

To investigate the use of elastic net regression approaches, assume that AM-FM components are rearranged along the columns of a matrix \mathbf{X} . Then, let $\beta = [\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p]^T$ denote the linear regression coefficients. In discrete space form, we rewrite equation (2) as a problem of estimating the optimal $\hat{\beta}$ so that the rearrange image \mathbf{I} , arranged along a column vector, can be approximated from the product $\mathbf{I} \approx \mathbf{X}\beta$.

A sparse and robust approximation can be obtained by minimizing $L(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \beta)$

$$L(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \beta) = \|\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|^2 + \lambda_1 \|\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda_2 \|\beta\|_1 \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ are represent weights on the squared ℓ^2 norm and the ℓ^1 norm. Sparsity is reframed as variable selection

Fig. 1. Gabor filterbank. The Gabor filterbank family is based on six different scales and eight different orientations with fixed radial frequencies as given in Table I.

in the formulation of the elastic net regression approach of Zou and Hastie [14]. The algorithm provided by Zou and Hastie in [14] estimates suitable values for λ_1, λ_2 . In (6), the minimization of the ℓ^1 norm produces a solution with a minimal number of regression coefficients while still providing good reconstruction accuracy as required by the first term and minimizing oscillations in the coefficients as controlled by the squared ℓ^2 norm. Clearly, by minimizing the number of regression coefficients, we also reduce the number of AM-FM components that are used in the reconstruction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Gabor filterbank framework is shown in Figure 1. A summary of image reconstruction results are given in Table II and III. Evaluation of the method based on reconstructions of the Lena image is shown in Figure 2, and for the building image (see [15]), the results are summarized in table III and Figures 3 and 4.

From Tables II and III, note that all methods give excellent reconstructions for high levels of overlap. This is further demonstrated in Figure 3 for the Lena image. However, as summarized in Table II and III, for reduced overlap, the proposed elastic net reconstructions perform significantly better than mDCA and DCA. Overall, we have that:

- 1) Elastic net component selection gave significantly better reconstruction performance over DCA and mDCA. Here, both mDCA and elastic net use 6 components.
- 2) The Gabor filterbank overlap index has a significant impact on the reconstruction quality.
- 3) Elastic net component selection capture directional components of the image as shown in the selected components of Fig. 3 for the buildings image of Fig. 4.

TABLE II
PSNR FOR RECONSTRUCTIONS OF THE LENA IMAGE. MULTISCALE DCA (MDCA) AND ELASTIC NET RECONSTRUCTIONS USE 6 COMPONENTS. DCA USES A SINGLE AM-FM COMPONENT.

Overlap Index	DCA	mDCA	Elastic Net
0.867	31.23	39.01	42.16
0.824	28.12	35.97	39.06
0.783	26.23	33.69	36.94
0.742	25.03	31.81	36.11
0.7	24.31	30.29	34.53
0.599	23.8	27.59	32.23
0.507	23.8	26.1	30.9
0.428	23.83	25.34	29.82
0.365	23.83	24.92	29.03

TABLE III
PSNR FOR RECONSTRUCTIONS OF THE BUILDING IMAGE. MULTISCALE DCA (MDCA) AND ELASTIC NET RECONSTRUCTIONS USE 6 COMPONENTS. DCA USES A SINGLE AM-FM COMPONENT.

Overlap Index	DCA	mDCA	Elastic Net
0.867	27.5	31.95	43.18
0.824	24.16	28.82	33.49
0.783	22.11	26.66	31.25
0.742	20.79	25.02	29.41
0.7	19.92	23.75	28.41
0.599	18.66	21.67	26.66
0.507	17.92	20.47	25.36
0.428	17.38	19.64	23.81
0.365	16.97	18.97	22.46

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of elastic net regression has produced excellent image reconstructions. More generally, all component selection methods give excellent reconstructions for high levels of overlap. Overall, the proposed approach gave significantly better reconstructions over all previously considered approaches. The proposed elastic net approach can provide a sparse representation based on AM-FM components derived from channel component analysis.

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Fig. 2. Reconstructions of the Lena image. (a) Original Lena Image (b) DCA Lena Reconstruction based on Gabor filterbank family with overlap index 0.867. PSNR= 31.23dB. (c) mDCA Lena Reconstruction based on Gabor filterbank family with overlap index 0.867 PSNR=39.01dB. (d) Elastic Net Lena Reconstruction based on Gabor filterbank family with overlap index 0.867, PSNR=42.16dB.

Fig. 3. Elastic net component selection for building image (see Fig. 4). The selected Gabor filters are marked. The directionality of the image forced the selection of horizontal and vertical components. This example uses a high overlap index of 0.95. The channel weights were set as follows: (1) component 41 has beta coefficient of 0.0043, (2) component 20 has a beta coefficient of -0.024, (3) component 11 has a beta coefficient of -0.099, (4) component 6 has a beta coefficient of 0.410, (5) component 5 has a beta coefficient of 0.237, and (6) component 1 has a beta coefficient of 0.657.

Fig. 4. Building image reconstruction based on elastic net regression (see Fig. 3). (a) Original building image from LIVE image database [14]. (b) Elastic net reconstruction based on Gabor filterbank.